

Pre-study questionnaire

* Indicates required question

1. Email *

2. 1. After reading the consent form sent to you by email. Do you consent to participate in this study? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

3. 2. What are your preferred pronouns? (Select all that apply) *

Check all that apply.

She/her

He/him

They/them

Ze/hir

Prefer not to answer

4. 3. What is your current role? *

Mark only one oval.

PMC member

Committer

Other: _____

5. 4. How long have you been in your current role? *

Mark only one oval.

Less than 1 year

1 to 2 years

3 to 5 years

6 to 10 years

Over 10 years

6. 5. Are regular contributions to Beam part of your primary employment? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

7. 6. Are you an Apache member? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Prefer not to answer

Please think about your project Beam when answered the following questions.

8. 7. In the past month, how much effort did you spend on *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not in my immediate agenda	Very little	Not as much as I want to	Moderate amount of effort	A lot
Optimizing pull request merge time	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Optimizing response time to issues	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Attracting a diverse group of contributors	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Retaining diverse contributors	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
Fostering a connected community	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

In this study we are looking at diversity from the perspective of gender and affiliation

Gender diversity: refers to the representation and inclusion of individuals of different genders in various settings such as workplaces, communities, and organizations.

Affiliation diversity: refers to the inclusion of individuals from organizations (ASF, Google, LinkedIn, etc), including those who are unaffiliated.

9. 8. Please rate your degree of agreement to the following statements *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I am aware of the state of gender diversity in my project	☐				
I plan to take action to improve gender diversity in my project	☐				
I am aware of the state of affiliation diversity in my project	☐				
I plan to take action to improve affiliation diversity in my project	☐				
I am aware of the turnover trend within my project	☐				
I plan to take action to improve turnover within my project	☐				

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